

ANALYSIS OF SOCIAL WORDS IN A FOREIGN LANGUAGE

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Annotation: This article analyzes the lexical changes that took place in the language of the press in post-revolutionary Iran in 1979, with some words appearing and replaced by others. Relationships between lexical units began to be studied in two ways. In the first direction, the interaction of lexemes such as synonyms, antonyms, homonyms, paronyms, graduonyms, hyponyms, paronyms, as well as the exchange of words within a lexeme, that is, in the second direction, the semantic structure of the lexeme has been replaced by new terms focused on words used in modern advertising.

Key words: Persian lexical system, linguistic field, historical books, the internal press, advertisements, ever-renewing press.

In the early twentieth century, the rise of systematic research in all disciplines in Iran, the recognition that language also has a systemic nature, the recognition of redundancy as a whole made up of interactions of elements has led to more human attention to the relationship between them and the internal press of an object rather than to the material side of the language being studied. The objective world around us has the property of internal divisibility as a whole system of mutually conditioned, interdependent elements. In the words of Professor Sh. Iskandarova, this division is reflected in the human mind in a generalized way and is expressed in language. The reflection of the universe in the human mind is conceptualization. It is for this reason that concepts such as the linguistic landscape of the Iranian state (in advertisements), the mythical landscape of the world (in historical books), and the scientific landscape of the world have emerged today. All of this is the result of the reflection of the universe in the human mind, and the linguistic view of the universe is understood as the expression of the cosmic system through the ever-renewing press language.

According to the exchange of words, the world around us is made up of the relationship between the penetration of new terms of the macro and micro worlds among the people. As the macrocosm for such press exchange is conceptualized in the human mind, these concepts are expressed differently in different languages. In the development of socio-political lexemes in the period of independence, the national mentality was also reflected in the social factor in the creation of national statehood. This can also be seen in the re-formation of terms and other obsolete

lexemes used in parallel with language units, such as language dictionaries, advertisements, social dialogue, and government names.

The emergence of the concept of the loss of the value of words (the replacement of the old word by a new one) led to the birth and development of the theory of the linguistic field in linguistics. Because the universe is reflected in the human mind divided into certain microcosmes, that is, paradigms. It is these paradigms in the universe that are reflected in the human mind that have their own linguistic expression, forming lexical paradigms. The lexical system of any language consists of the interrelation of several paradigms united on the basis of a certain commonality of meaning. On the basis of such common meaning, the paradigm of linguistic units united in our memory is the linguistic field. In other words, a set of linguistic units that reflect the conceptual, subjective, or functional similarity of events that are combined and defined on the basis of a particular semantic commonality is defined as a linguistic field.

It is known that the changes that take place in the life of the state and society in the development of any language have a great influence as an important extralinguistic factor. The macro-social factor of the last 40 years has also led to radical changes in the socio-political lexicon in relation to other layers of language vocabulary, based on which the following changes can be made:

Activation of socio-political lexemes. This means an increase in the frequency of use of some terms and terms related to the political sphere, that is, they are widely used not only in the speech of experts in the field, but also by speakers of this language. The process of activation is more common than other phenomena in the lexical norms of the socio-political sphere. This can also be seen in the terms in each ad and when the activation process takes place.

The development of meaning in socio-political lexemes. At the same time, changes such as the increase in the amount of meaning in the semantic structure of lexical units and the expansion of the volume of meaning were taken into account. Linguist A.Kuranbekov said, “Semantic word formation is the use of a word in a new sense, the change of the meaning of a word is its development. As long as the meaning of a word changes and it has a different meaning, the next one should be considered a new word compared to the previous one.” The following appearances of semantically constructed words were identified.

If the concept of new terms led to the emergence of the theory of the linguistic field, the processes of globalization and integration that took place at the end of the twentieth century led to the further actualization of this theory. In the words of Y. Khamraeva, “The development of science and technology has dramatically changed the vocabulary of languages in the world. As a result, there is a growing focus on

collecting all the lexical units in the lexical reserve or in a particular area of social life and interpreting them within the paradigms (semantic fields) to which it belongs. ”

In short, the theory of the concept of advertising is widely developed in modern world linguistics. A number of works have been published devoted to the study of a number of fields, such as the field of respect for the Persian language, the field of anemonics, the field of personality, the field of kinship. In addition, the full coverage of the relationship of the Persian lexical system to the objective world system is based on the study of what semantic fields (paradigms) of the Persian lexicon, the internal structure of these semantic fields and the relationship of structural units, the organic connection of each field. closely related.

According to the associative relationship between the lexical-semantic system, the hierarchical division of lexemes corresponds to the hierarchical division of political advertising. Therefore, forms of social consciousness, such as politics, morality, religion, law, in the lexical system of the Persian language form groups of "social advertising" of socio-political lexicon, socio-moral lexicon, socio-religious lexicon and political terms.

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